

‘Beastial Communications’: Race, Friendship, and Factionalism in the Madras Army, 1832-1837

Callie Wilkinson, MSCA Postdoctoral Fellow^{a*}

^a School of History, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich, Munich, Germany

* Callie.Wilkinson@lrz.uni-muenchen.de

**Funded by
the European Union**

‘Beastial Communications’: Race, Friendship, and Factionalism in the Madras Army, 1832-1837

Historians of empire have long been interested in how interpersonal relationships between colonizer and colonized did or did not conform to imperial ideologies. Yet, the relationships that developed between European and Indian officers in the East India Company’s armies remain largely unexplored. This is an important omission, because the armies employed thousands of people and represented a significant point of cross-cultural contact. This article uses the variety of materials generated by a controversy in the Fifth Light Cavalry, Madras Army to understand the nature and limits of what contemporaries called friendships. Both parties in the controversy, as well as apparently neutral onlookers, testified to the existence of friendships and factions that bridged race and rank. These were vertical relationships of service and obligation; Indian officers sought the goodwill of their superiors to ensure their professional security, while British officers looked to Indian allies for information and legitimacy. When disputes broke out between rival British officers, however, Indian allies risked becoming collateral damage, while British officers were singled out for punishment for betraying fellow gentlemen. Through this controversy, we see how and why hierarchies of race and rank were undermined, as well as the mechanisms whereby they were ultimately preserved intact.

Keywords: race; army; sepoys; empire; East India Company; Madras; South Asia; Britain; military law; friendship; patronage.

Word count: 13,691

Introduction

In 1835, a British officer with twenty years of military service under his belt was dismissed from the Madras Army for gossiping with an Indian non-commissioned officer (NCO). Their conversations concerned acts of sodomy allegedly committed by another British officer and entered the official record during a military trial. These ‘beastial communications’ (as the prosecution called them) then became the subject of a general court martial in their own right.¹ In a profession governed by rigid codes of

honour, being tried for gossip was not unusual; similar charges could be and often were brought because of rumours circulated by European officers.² In this case, however, the defendant, Major John Watkins, insisted that he was being punished for ‘attempting to treat a native as a friend’.³ The story exposes the institutional racism that was prevalent in the armies of the British East India Company (EIC), while also suggesting that affiliations along racial lines were not preordained. Watkins, at least, had assumed that European and Indian officers could be ‘friends’, a relationship which, during this period, was understood predominantly in terms of reciprocal obligations.⁴ As historian Naomi Tadmor explains, ‘the moral duty of “friends” was to stand by each other, and, if necessary, “serve” each other as best they could’.⁵ This article uses the print and manuscript material generated by this case to explore the nature and limits of these friendships. In the process, it shows how boundaries of race and rank were constructed, reproduced, and contested in imperial armed forces.

One of the most notorious features of the nineteenth-century EIC was its reliance on Indian soldiers, known as sepoy. Over the centuries European colonizers commonly exploited the military labour of the colonized, but the sheer scale of the EIC’s recruiting made them distinct. From the mid-eighteenth century, the number of sepoy in the EIC’s service increased rapidly, from roughly 9,000 in 1765, to 155,000 in 1808, to 200,000 on the eve of its demise in 1856.⁶ At its height the EIC commanded some of the largest standing armies of its time, wherein, according to its own calculations, the proportion of European to native troops reached 5,110 to one by 1830.⁷ To contemporaries, these armies were, as one handbook described them, ‘the most remarkable phenomenon in the history of the world, since conquerors thought of making the vanquished the means of their own perpetual subjugation.’⁸ Given their sheer numbers and strategic importance, the possibility of a sepoy mutiny was a

recognized threat to the EIC's survival, and the armies regarded in the light of a 'powerful, but most dangerous instrument.'⁹ British-authored texts of the period speculated endlessly about sepoys' affective states: whether they were loyal, and how they could be made loyal. One commonly proposed solution to the problem was to build rapport between sepoys and their European officers.

Despite the importance invested in these relationships in the nineteenth century, historians of the EIC have not devoted much attention to how they worked in practice. Historian Douglas Peers has analysed these discourses, arguing that racial and ethnographic thinking led to the early adoption of a paternalistic officer ideal in the EIC's armies.¹⁰ More recently, Christina Welsch has shown how European officers justified the EIC's system of 'stratocracy', or rule by the army, by emphasizing their ability to control sepoys.¹¹ Still, histories of life in camps and cantonments have emphasized separation, pointing out that sepoys lived, ate, and socialized in their own lines.¹² The Indian officers who stood at the interface between sepoys and European officers, meanwhile, have not been taken seriously as cultural brokers. Despite a proliferation of studies on go-betweens in other branches of the EIC's service, the armies have not received this treatment, meaning that Indian officers continue to be understood in terms of nineteenth-century stereotypes. In a representative refrain, Peers writes that 'they possessed little influence and were given barely any respect from either their officers or the sepoys beneath them.'¹³ This is certainly the picture that emerges from many British military memoirs. Consulting the military justice, archive, however, reveals evidence of interaction, negotiation, and alliance-making.

In studying these interactions, we can learn how far norms and expectations translated (or not) into individual relationships. Historians have long been interested in how imperialism shaped interpersonal relationships and vice versa, although the

friendships formed in the cantonment have not featured prominently in this literature. Ann Stoler has influentially argued for the importance of intimacy and affect in histories of empire, emphasizing colonial states' preoccupation with the regulation of affiliation and desire.¹⁴ Imperial institutions might promote particular 'emotional regimes' designed to create and sustain divisions between colonizer and colonized, but individuals did not always respect these conventions, as Will Jackson has pointed out.¹⁵ Perhaps the most well-known example of this is Leela Gandhi's study of how, in the late nineteenth century, friendships between British and South Asian radicals contributed to an atmosphere of 'affective cosmopolitanism' that contravened imperial hierarchies of race and gender.¹⁶ Friendships, she argues, could have subversive potential.

The scandal in the Fifth Light Cavalry, however, exposes the limits of friendship as well as its possibilities. The friendships described by Gandhi, informed as they were by the utopian socialism of the late nineteenth century, differ markedly from the relationships featured here, which, from a twenty-first century perspective, may not seem much like friendships at all. In the early nineteenth century, friendship and patronage were intertwined. Friendship was not necessarily conceived as a relationship between equals; the term commonly referred to vertical relationships of service and obligation as well as to more affective ties between likeminded people.¹⁷ Friendships thus operated differently in this period, predicated on a different set of assumptions about what was owed and to who. Even so, these obligations could pull in different directions, at times upholding the status quo, at times undermining it. Different friendships could come into conflict, and, as this article will show, people sometimes disagreed about how best to evaluate competing claims to friendship. Understanding these dynamics can help us understand both the resources available to the Indian

officers and NCOs employed by the EIC, as well as the obstacles they faced in negotiating its institutional culture.

The distinctive social life of the army is worth studying because here the intimacy and the violence characteristic of imperial encounters was particularly acute. While Stoler identified kitchens, bedrooms, and nurseries as ‘intimate frontiers’ where ‘racial classifications were defined and defied’, the public spaces of army camps and cantonments also fit this description.¹⁸ The EIC’s armies enabled sustained cross-cultural interaction on a large scale by requiring thousands of Europeans and Indians to live and work in relative proximity. As Durba Ghosh, Erica Wald, and Kenneth Ballhatchet have shown, a spectrum of intimate relations between European men and Indian women proliferated within the army, from prostitution to cohabitation.¹⁹ Though less well-studied, camps and cantonments were also important sites for the development of relationships between men. The perceived importance of esprit de corps meant that feelings of loyalty and solidarity were actively cultivated within the army; as historian Scott Myerly has indicated, it was by fostering these feelings that soldiers were transformed into manageable ‘tools of war’.²⁰ The experience of fighting side by side was also believed to forge bonds that superseded differences of race and rank; according to one Madras Army officer, ‘there is nothing so efficacious in destroying the feelings of mutual prejudice as the sense of mutual dependence.’²¹ Still, armies are rigidly hierarchical institutions; in the nineteenth century the army was an important site for the institutionalization of racial difference in colonial India, introducing strict rules limiting Indians from positions of authority as well as spatially segregating them in camps and cantonments.²² As Elizabeth Kolsky has demonstrated, violence was rife within these spaces, and indeed at the heart of the scandal discussed here were allegations of physical assault and abuse.²³ Although military authorities worked hard to conciliate

Indian personnel, these soldiers were nevertheless exposed to racism and violence of all kinds, including from their supposed brothers in arms. Across the nineteenth century, European officers were repeatedly instructed in General Orders to ‘use your best exertions to check ... this offensive, and in some cases, inhuman behaviour.’²⁴ As this article will show, these abuses co-existed alongside exchanges of information and services which contemporaries described as friendly.

To capture these complex dynamics, this article focuses on a lingering scandal that troubled the Fifth Light Cavalry (LC) in the years 1827 to 1835, when Lieutenant Colonel Edward Lloyd Smythe, after being investigated, tried, and then acquitted of sodomy, promptly sued Major John Watkins, his prosecutor. Unfortunately, the controversy cannot tell us much about sodomy in the army. The alleged assaults are perhaps surprisingly marginal to the dispute; Watkins claimed that he never believed in Smythe’s guilt, and Smythe, for his part, seemed satisfied that his acquittal had exonerated him in the eyes of the public. Instead, the two debated the degree to which Watkins had actively propagated rumours of sodomy in the regiment. In disputing this point, they reveal much about the interactions between European officers and their Indian counterparts. To be sure, no single case study can capture the diversity of relationships that may have existed in the Madras Army. Still, the variety of evidence generated by this case (including petitions, pamphlets, trial transcripts, official correspondence, and newspaper coverage) provides a rare glimpse into an aspect of life in the EIC’s armies that is often elided in official records or in the personal correspondence of European officers. Through this case, we acquire some insight into the largely lost encounters that occurred on the parade or on the threshold of officer’s bungalows.

In recounting and contextualizing this story, this article shows how and why British and Indian officers formed friendships, and with what consequences. Section one describes the ambivalent social dynamics in the EIC's armies, where Europeans were deliberately separated from Indian soldiers but also instructed to build a rapport with them. Section two briefly tells the story of the scandal that erupted in the Fifth LC, focusing on the porosity of the boundaries between officers' bungalows and native lines. Section three analyses the scandal, drawing on what we know about army life in India to understand how these relationships worked and when and why they broke down. Indian officers benefited from character references and recommendations but could become collateral damage to disputes between Europeans. The events in the Fifth LC, however, suggest that British officers may have been singled out for punishment in these situations. Belonging to gentlemanly society conferred many privileges and protections, but it also entailed obligations. Although European officers were under pressure to cultivate the loyalties of Indian officers, they were nevertheless expected to preserve hierarchies of race and rank. Officers who broke these codes risked serious social and professional sanctions. The fact that officers sometimes did so reflects, not so much their commitment to equality, but rather the illegibility of the EIC's protocols, which explicitly enjoined officers to conciliate Indian soldiers but implicitly set limits to these relationships. The personal and professional consequences of transgressing these boundaries could be serious, but where and when the line should be drawn was unclear. The scandal in the Fifth LC, in other words, suggests that social life within the cantonment may have been more diverse, complicated, and contentious than previously thought.

Regimental Relationships

The EIC began forming regular sepoy battalions in the mid-eighteenth century. Initially dependent on Indian contractors to fill their ranks, gradually the EIC developed their own recruitment networks, partly by drawing on the friends and kin of those already in their service.²⁵ The composition of these Indian or 'native' regiments, as they were called, varied regionally. The EIC had three armies, corresponding to the three Presidencies or administrative divisions of Bengal, Bombay, and Madras. Each possessed its own recruiting base. The native regiments of the Madras cavalry, the focus of this article, were originally inherited from the nawab of Arcot and continued to be associated predominantly with Muslim noblemen from the Carnatic during this period.²⁶

Historians have advanced different, overlapping explanations for why these men might have entered the Company's service. The phenomenon is not unique to South Asia. Around the world, colonized populations joined the British empire's burgeoning armed forces as a means of making claims upon the colonial state. In India, access to reliable lines of credit gave the EIC an advantage within the military labour market; they were better positioned to pay wages on time and could supply pensions to soldiers who grew old in their service.²⁷ Sepoys could also channel the EIC's influence when needed; in the allied state of Awadh, for example, sepoy from the Bengal Army appealed to the Company's agent in the capital for protection and redress in land and legal disputes.²⁸ Finally, the Company's expanding political influence meant that alternative options were limited. As nominally independent but practically subordinate Indian kingdoms were not only drained of the necessary wealth but in some cases denied the right to maintain large standing armies, serving the Company was sometimes the best way for men retain their status and occupation.²⁹

Opportunities for advancement, however, were circumscribed by the racial logic according to which the EIC's armies were organized. From 1784, positions of command were restricted to European officers.³⁰ Indians could still become commissioned officers, but only through seniority, as a reward for long years of service. Promotion within the Company's European officer corps operated according to strict seniority, too, but there were key differences that put Indian officers at a disadvantage. First, European officers and NCOs always enjoyed seniority over their Indian counterparts; as a *Blackwoods* correspondent opined, 'we have a class of men, doing duty as officers, and really such, exposed to the degradation of being placed under the control of a non-commissioned officer, merely because the face of the one happens to be of a brown colour, and the face of the other yellow'.³¹ This custom was made more painful by a second feature of the system, whereby Europeans entered the officer corps directly as cadets, whereas Indian officers had to work their way up from the ranks. Consequently, Indian officers with decades of experience were subordinate to new arrivals from Britain, and therefore, to quote soldier and author John Malcolm, vulnerable to 'the harshness of a European officer, a boy, perhaps, who has just joined that corps to which he, the native officer, has perhaps belonged for thirty or forty years.'³² The British rank and file, meanwhile, were segregated into a separate European branch of the service, meaning that, as one memoirist summarized it, 'in no case does a native command a European.'³³

Indian soldiers were marked out in another way, through the arrangements made for their accommodation and subsistence. Whereas European private soldiers lived in communal barracks provided by the EIC, sepoys were supplied with materials to build their own huts and make their own messing arrangements.³⁴ Their quarters were separate from the barracks, and from the bungalows inhabited by European officers.

The principle of segregation was informed partly by disciplinary concerns, namely, the desire to insulate sepoys from the unruly European rank and file, but also by medical theories that associated Indian habitations with dirt, disorder, and disease.³⁵ Investing sepoys with control over their own living conditions had the added advantage of reducing trouble and expense on the Company's side, while mitigating the possibility of ritual pollution.³⁶ According to the spatial logic of the cantonment, then, Indians and Europeans were separated, except for when they met on parade for the purposes of discipline and drill. As Douglas Peers interprets it, 'Once their duty was complete, and they returned to their own lines, colonial authority quickly receded, and with it the possibility of making a more significant cultural imprint on the sepoy.'³⁷

Given these circumstances, one would assume that a relatively limited role was envisaged for European officers; in fact, the opposite was true. European officers were commonly described as the vital link in the chain binding sepoys to the EIC, an idea which, as Christina Welsch has reminded us, officers themselves were keen to exploit.³⁸ European officers were expensive to maintain but justified this expense on the grounds that Indian regiments could not function without them. Their arguments were premised on the assumption that Indians responded best to active management and authoritarian styles of rule, and that they required a European officer's formative influence to mould them into fighting men.³⁹ A correspondent of *The Oriental Herald* claimed that '[n]o people are so malleable', such that '[w]hatever the Native troops have been, are now, or will be, has depended, and must ever depend, not upon them, but upon ourselves.'⁴⁰

The Company's outsider status made the establishment and exercise of this influence even more important. Sepoys had no reason to love a conquering power; if they developed affective ties to the army, it was, so British contemporaries believed, more likely to be because of personal connections formed while in the service. During

an 1831 parliamentary inquiry, expert witnesses emphasized the importance of the European officer in securing sepoys' contingent loyalties. British Army officer Jasper Nicolls (1778-1849), who served in India and was later appointed commander-in-chief in India in 1839, replied that 'the principal bond of attachment to the service, to the state in fact, is through the medium of the officer.'⁴¹ Captain Turner Macan (1792-1836), another British Army officer who served in India and became a Persian interpreter, elaborated: 'I do not imagine that there was ever any strong attachment in the native troops to the Company's service or to the English in the abstract; they were attached to particular leaders.'⁴² Holt Mackenzie (1786-1876), an EIC administrator, concurred that 'in many corps the sepoys have a great deal of personal attachment to their English officers; but that attachment seems to rest rather upon the personal character and conduct of the individual officers than upon anything that might be called an attachment to the nation generally.'⁴³ Though pessimistic about sepoys' attachment to the EIC, contemporaries surmised that they might remain loyal to a good officer.

Because of this interrelated set of assumptions, when a rash of mutinies and desertions broke out in the 1820s, they were attributed in part to a failure in leadership. Seema Alavi has identified the 1820s as a 'crisis of control' brought on by military cuts and retrenchments, exacerbated by the insistence of sepoys on the high-caste status that the Company had previously worked hard to cultivate.⁴⁴ As Douglas Peers has demonstrated, the early reversals of the First Anglo-Burmese War (1824-6), coupled with the bloody repression of a mutiny at Barrackpur (1824), resulted in a period of anxious reflection regarding the condition of the army. While the preponderance of demanding high-caste recruits was advanced as one problem, the attenuation of the bonds between officer and sepoy was identified as another.⁴⁵ History was invoked to support this interpretation. Responding to critics of the native soldiery, one anonymous

pamphleteer recalled the role that earlier generations of sepoys had played in the conquest of Bengal, arguing that ‘their descendants of the present day, would follow with unabated ardour, and undeteriorated qualities, any commander who understood their character, respected their prejudices, or regarded their affections.’⁴⁶ The achievements of Robert Clive (1725-1774) suggested that European officers could lead sepoys to victory; if they failed, it was because they had failed in their duty as officers.

This duty included conciliation. In General Orders, British officers were repeatedly instructed to cultivate good relations with their Indian counterparts. In one directive from the EIC’s court of directors published to the army, the directors emphasized ‘the absolute necessity that must ever exist of conciliating the minds of the native officers and soldiers, and particularly of the former, by the most mild and considerate treatment’, which the directors regarded to be an ‘essential branch of their duty’.⁴⁷ While sepoys had good reasons for enlisting in the EIC’s armies, military authorities understood that to secure a sepoy’s allegiance, they had to treat him well and compensate him accordingly. Deeply embedded theories of Asiatic despotism predisposed some British officers to see Indians as naturally suited to the army’s hierarchical structures: ‘In that patient population, trained for ages to un murmuring obedience to despotic authority, insubordination is scarcely ever heard of’, wrote one military author approvingly. Still, within the same text, the author conceded that ‘I do not think that the natives in general are much pleased with our sway,’ leading him to recommend ‘paying them liberally, providing for the comforts of their families, and taking especial care not to allow their faith to be insulted by any persons.’⁴⁸ Contrary to the Asiatic despotism stereotype, recurring mutinies demonstrated that sepoys’ compliance could not be taken for granted. As another officer described it, ‘the government has at all times felt convinced that its existence depended upon the

excellence of the army, and its fidelity to the state, and has therefore adopted every measure which was likely to lead to its improvement, or to conciliate the affections of its native soldiery.’⁴⁹

To effectively pursue a policy of conciliation, an officer needed to be able to identify and understand soldiers’ discontents before they festered. To do so, British officers relied on the information supplied by Indian officers. ‘A Madras Officer’, writing to the *Calcutta Journal*, regarded Indian officers as ‘a most important link in the Military chain which unites the Colonel of the Regiment and the lowest rank in it’, and suggested that ‘without them, no Native Regiment could be managed.’ Because Indian troops lived separately from Europeans, ‘[i]t is therefore absolutely necessary that there should be some class of men who, being of the same castes as the men, can mingle with them at all times’, and whose status as commissioned officers gave them a stake in upholding the status quo.⁵⁰ Without the aid of native officers, Europeans had little hope of effectively monitoring the mood in the native lines.

Some doubted whether Indian officers could be trusted to fulfil this intermediary function. In a letter to the editor of the *Asiatic Journal*, anonymous contributor Carnaticus described Indian officers as ‘entirely unfit for the responsibility or duties that generally attach to the designation of officers’ owing to their advanced age. Carnaticus admitted that commissions for Indian officers fulfilled a social function, providing a sop for frustrated ambition by ‘holding out, to the Native army at large, some little opening of advancement, and offering some apology for the entire supplanting of their natural pretensions’. Still, Indian officers as a group were, he thought, dangerous and untrustworthy; the letter alluded to ‘plots and defections’ at Travancore, Java, and Nagpur, that originated ‘not from any provocations or wrong, on our parts, but from their hearts – their jealousy and distaste of us.’⁵¹ Carnaticus identified a vicious cycle:

British imperial dominance limited opportunities for Indian officers and this in turn was suspected of causing resentments; yet, it was precisely these resentments (real or imagined) that deterred some officers from entrusting their Indian counterparts with greater responsibilities.

Not everyone believed that Indian and European officers were predestined to come into conflict. Military memoirist Major Henry Bevan (Madras Native Infantry, 1808-38) felt that 'jealousy between native and European officers has been greatly exaggerated'. Referring to the convention, 'frequently asserted', 'that the condition of the native officers is so very anomalous that it must of necessity lead to the agitation of awkward questions of precedence', Bevan claimed that 'I have not heard of any such being mooted', though he admitted that 'the constitution of native officers is not unlikely to lead to such discussions'. Bevan did concede that European and Indian officers did not socialize much, though he argued that religious difference was the primary barrier to greater intimacy: 'Religious prejudices, on the part of natives, have more effect in keeping up this distinction than the aristocratic reluctance of English officers to mix with persons who have risen from the ranks.' Still, based on 'personal experience', Bevan argued 'that the native officers are anxious to do all in their power to contribute to the comfort of their European commander.'⁵² Bevan believed that British and Indian officers could work together in harmony, but his views were based on personal experience of acts of kindness performed by Indians subordinate to him in rank; he wrote from a position of privilege, not as one whose social and professional horizons were circumscribed by the intersecting forces of race, rank, and religion.

A different perspective is provided by a seditious pamphlet, authored by a regimental *munshi* (writer or secretary) and circulated in Madras Army cantonments at Secunderabad, Jaulna, and Arcot in the 1830s. The pamphlet was composed in response

to missionary tracts that had been distributed to the native cavalry of the Madras Army in 1833. The intention was to defend the Muslim faith by providing a thorough-going refutation of Christianity; the substance of the argument was that Christians were hypocrites who did not practice what they preached.⁵³ To support this claim, the author described objectionable aspects of the British lifestyle, which included drinking on Sunday, failing to discipline their wives, and venerating the flag of their nation above the symbols of their religion.⁵⁴ More relevant for our purposes, however, is what the pamphlet has to say about friendship between Europeans and Indians in the army.

The text is, in brief, pessimistic. The anonymous author concurred that religious differences posed an insurmountable barrier to trust; the pamphlet declares that ‘no dependence is to be placed on the word and no belief in their (the English) friendship according to the proverb there is no dependence to be placed on the promises of the kafirs and faithless ones.’ Yet, the text also identifies a further source of complaint, namely, that Indians who performed favours for Europeans were not repaid in kind: ‘whether it be the powerful friend or the servant, what is the reward of either when their (the English) designs are fully accomplished it is thus “we do not know you”.⁵⁵ To illustrate, the text recounts the story of a naik (Indian NCO corresponding to a corporal) who reported on a woman who was fraudulently drawing a pension from government, ‘and although this information was correct and supported by many witnesses after enquiry it was decided that the naik was a mischiefmaker and he was punished and discharged the service’.⁵⁶ According to the text, ‘it is notorious to all that should any person through attachment give information of any sedition, he is himself instantly placed in confinement and in such circumstances, neither their promises nor agreements can be depended upon’.⁵⁷ A man might be rewarded for his performance on the battlefield, but ‘in any other case the only reward of fidelity is punishment.’⁵⁸

Commentaries like these provide valuable evidence about the perspectives of Indians employed by the EIC, but they are few and far between for this period. The pamphlet was copied by hand and circulated in small numbers; the only reason it has survived is because it was deemed seditious, reported, and subjected to an official investigation, which meant, in turn, that extracts from it were translated and preserved in the official proceedings. Though filtered through the lens of the interests and priorities of the EIC itself, the EIC's disciplinary records remain perhaps the best source of insight into how the relationships between Indian and British officers operated in practice.

The adjudication of honour crimes, in particular, can shed light on the tensions that sometimes surfaced in the army. 'Conduct unbecoming an officer and gentleman' was the most common charge levelled against officers at court martial during this period, but remained undefined, functioning as a flexible device for disciplining officers who contravened an often-unspoken code. Courts martial were accorded this discretion because of the importance of honour within the officer corps, and the difficulty of predicting the thousand different ways in which it might be breached.⁵⁹ In the nineteenth century, officers were expected to adhere to particular social codes which reflected the hierarchical nature of the army as an institution; an officer was expected to be loyal to the commander, was discouraged from consorting with the rank and file, and was regarded as belonging to a brotherhood of officers who were empowered to punish him with social and legal sanctions if he stepped out of line.⁶⁰ One possible offence was 'associating with private soldiers, and others of inferior rank in society', which might include, for example, drinking in barracks and public houses with enlisted men.⁶¹ The documentation generated by these cases can therefore help us understand how

hierarchies of race and rank were enacted and upheld in the armies, as well as pointing out when and why they might be breached.

Officially, the protocol for handling perceived infringements of this code was clear. First, a written complaint would be transmitted to the adjutant, who would then inform the commanding officer. If deemed legitimate, the commanding officer would launch an investigation. The next step was a court of inquiry, wherein witnesses would be examined and cross-examined (albeit not under oath). Based on this pre-trial, the court would decide whether the complaint merited a full trial by court martial. Officers (or rank and file soldiers guilty of serious crimes) were tried at general courts martial, where thirteen officers would vote on their guilt or innocence; their sentence would then pass to the governor general for his approval. The rules of evidence were the same as in a civil court, but this evidence was not prepared or presented by lawyers; instead, the defence and the prosecution made their case directly, issuing opening and closing statements as well as examining and counter-examining witnesses.⁶² General courts martial were differentiated along racial lines based on the race of the accused, according to the principle of trial by peers. Yet, so-called native trials were still overseen by a European judge advocate who was supposed to fulfil a tutelary function, while European witnesses could, and did, play an important part at native trials, and vice versa.⁶³

Alongside these official proceedings (always recorded but unevenly preserved) were the court martial narratives penned by interested parties. These texts comprised a distinctive genre wherein pamphleteers excerpted the transcript of a court martial but framed it as part of a longer story accompanied by critical commentary. Court-martial narratives made heavy use of official documents to achieve an appearance of objectivity and verisimilitude. Yet, the very purpose of these narratives was usually to furnish

information that the author claimed had been deliberately excluded from official proceedings.⁶⁴ As such, court martial narratives make for frustrating reading; they promise to expose the reality behind the scenes, but their claims can never be taken at face value. Perhaps this explains their neglected status. EIC officers wrote many such narratives, but these sources are rarely, if ever, used. As stories intended to convince, however, court martial narratives are indicative of broader discourses; after all, they were designed to appeal to public opinion and to play on common assumptions. By comparing them with official records and rival narratives, moreover, we can begin to better understand contemporary reactions to the scandals that sometimes erupted in the cantonment, even if the facts of the case remain elusive. Whereas many courts martial narratives are obsessed with questions of precedence, others, particularly the case study analysed here, furnish rare glimpses of a world of interactions. Through this combination of materials, we can begin to elucidate the relationships that developed within the cantonment.

‘The Evil Feeling’ in the Fifth Light Cavalry

The circumstances leading to the trooper’s death will never be known with certainty; the story was subject to speculation even at the time. All anyone knew for sure was the outcome. In May 1827, Trooper Lal Mahomed shot his commanding officer Lieutenant Colonel Edward Lloyd Smythe, briefly evaded capture, and then was shot himself. Smythe survived; Lal Mahomed did not. According to subsequent testimony, several different motives for the attempted assassination were canvassed by soldiers on site. The one that stuck was that Smythe had attempted sodomy. As rumour would have it (and as multiple native officers testified), Lal Mahomed rode up to the horse lines and cried out to his comrades to *‘Live happy, as he had shot the great sodomite.’* The

rumour prompted magisterial and police inquiries as well as a private investigation by the adjutant. Despite a petition presented by Lal Mahomed's sister and a formal complaint lodged by his brother, these investigations were eventually dropped, purportedly because of a lack of evidence.⁶⁵

The rumour would probably have been stifled by neglect had it not become associated with unrest within the regiment and thus tied to the fate of Major John Watkins, Smythe's successor. Watkins was on furlough in England when the failed assassination attempt occurred. On his return to the Fifth in 1828, Watkins heard the stories circulating about Smythe, but purportedly dismissed them. Once Watkins himself took command in the summer of 1829, however, he found the persistent allegations harder to ignore. Not long after Smythe left the regiment, Watkins was presented with an *arzee* or petition from the Indian officers of the Fifth LC requesting Smythe's return. The petition was transmitted to Watkins by a havildar major called Yusuf Khan. When Watkins asked Yusuf Khan to explain why the men preferred Smythe, the havildar major is supposed to have replied that the authors of the petition were sodomites. In May 1832, Watkins was presented with another address, this time from a jemadar⁶⁶ protesting his supersession by a man junior to him; this address, too, alluded to purported acts of sodomy by Smythe, and attributed the unrest within the regiment to the intrigues of Subadar Ahmed Khan (one of Smythe's rumoured favourites).⁶⁷ The address instigated a court of inquiry, and upon the recommendation of the court Subadar Ahmed Khan was tried for three instances of insubordination: first, for privately urging native officers assembled at his house to oust Watkins from the command on the grounds that 'if Major Watkins joins the regiment he will find out what has been going on, and we shall all be ruined'; second, for having, in camp, declared publicly that Watkins intended to pension off seven native officers on a quarter of their

pay; and, finally, for declaring to the A Troop of the Fifth that Watkins had kept them too long at cleaning, ‘and if we are worked in this way now, how shall we be worked when we make long marches, and have our families to attend to.’⁶⁸ Subadar Ahmed Khan was acquitted, but insinuations of sodomy had now entered the official record; a court of inquiry, then a general court martial, were organized to investigate them.⁶⁹

The charges considered by the court of inquiry were issued by twenty-two persons between ages eleven and thirty-eight and involved twenty-nine different acts of sodomy or attempted sodomy over a period of twenty-five years. Based on the findings of this court of inquiry, Smythe was tried at Vizagapatam on 29 July 1833. According to military law, Smythe could only be tried for one charge at a time. Out of the many accusations levelled against him, one was selected: that, on 27 June 1817, Smythe had assaulted and sodomized Peer Khan, a trooper in the Fifth LC.⁷⁰ The official charge was buggery (an act of anal penetration). Buggery had been a capital offence in England since the sixteenth century. Anything less than actual penetration was prosecuted as a misdemeanour, usually assault (regardless of consent). Attempted sodomy was the more common charge, being less specific and easier to prove.⁷¹ Trying Smythe for buggery was risky, and he was acquitted.

For Smythe, the trial was just the beginning of the campaign to clear his name. After the governor general appended a lengthy remark to the published proceedings that reprimanded the court for refusing to allow the prosecution the use of character evidence, Smythe countered with a pamphlet that identified three injustices that had impeded his defence: the remote location of the trial; the mistreatment of witnesses; and the withholding of important documents.⁷² In addition to showing that his acquittal was a triumph of truth against the odds, Smythe also brought charges against a few fellow officers who, he felt, were primarily responsible for sowing the seeds of scandal. First to

be tried was Colonel Thomas Henry Somerset Conway, adjutant general of the Madras Army, who was charged and then acquitted of scandalous and infamous conduct unbecoming the character of an officer and a gentleman for suggesting to a fellow European officer that the accusations of sodomy were true.⁷³ Smythe's primary target, however, was Major John Watkins, who had acted as prosecutor at Smythe's court martial. At Smythe's instigation, the major was charged with conduct unbecoming an officer and a gentleman in three instances. First, for having 'surreptitiously held private conversations, deeply aspersing my character, with Troop Havildar-Major Yoosoof Khan, of the Fifth Regiment of Light Cavalry, and making no report to me thereof'. Second, for 'withholding from me all information touching infamous reports regarding me, communicated to him by the said Troop Havildar-Major Yoosoof Khan, as existing in the Regiment'. Finally, for 'by thus listening, without taking any further steps, to the said Troop Havildar-Major Yoosoof Khan, encouraging him to defame my character'.⁷⁴

Although Watkins was dismissed from the army, Smythe's vendetta did not end there; he was convinced that the major had not acted alone. Instead, Smythe tried to clear the cavalry of hostile forces. When Smythe wrote to the adjutant general demanding the ignominious dismissal of the individuals whom he believed had been implicated in the conspiracy, however, his request was refused. The commander in chief did consult the brigadier general, asking him to produce a confidential report on the question; his own conviction, however, was that it would be wrong to remove three native officers and nineteen NCOs and privates based on mere hearsay. If there were any substance to Smythe's complaint, the commander in chief felt, Smythe had, after all, the option of bringing the charges to court.⁷⁵

Still, the council were uneasy about 'the Evil Feeling avowedly Existing among the Native Ranks of the 5th Light cavalry'.⁷⁶ No obvious solution presented itself.

Pensioning them all off would be expensive; dispersing the men to other regiments merely presented ‘the risque of spreading Discord instead of extinguishing it.’⁷⁷ Whatever action they might take threatened to resurrect the controversy, ‘the Discussion of which is strictly forbidden’.⁷⁸ In his confidential report on the subject, Brigadier General Doveton initially recommended ‘the removal from the service of every man in any way implicated in the late Proceedings to whatever party he may belong’, declaring that ‘there can be no peace or quiet until this is effected.’⁷⁹ When the council wrote back the following year to follow up on his report, however, Doveton had changed his mind, believing that ‘the revival at this late period of an unpleasant subject which has so long been allowed to remain dormant could be productive of no good.’⁸⁰ In the end, the Military Department determined simply to pension off those who, whether from injury or long service, were eligible for retirement. These included two of the witnesses who had appeared at the original court of inquiry, including Jemadar Ismael Khan (a confidant of Watkins) and Jemadar Hussein Khan, who was singled out as ‘having been deeply engaged in the late unfortunate disputes.’⁸¹

Meanwhile, Watkins printed his own petition, and, in so doing, provided a different but complementary view of developments in the regiment. Watkins’s argument hinged on the fact that the rumours about Smythe were widely known. The implications of this were threefold. First, that it would have made no sense for Watkins to punish or report Yusuf Khan since the havildar major was not the author of the rumours but was merely repeating the talk current in the cantonment.⁸² Second, that it was absurd to hold Watkins accountable for conversations with Yusuf Khan when Yusuf Khan was known to have exchanged words to the same effect with other officers.⁸³ Finally, that there was no need to report the rumour to Smythe since it was impossible, given the many

inquiries into the case, that Smythe was not already aware of it.⁸⁴ The rumour, Watkins argued, had polluted the very atmosphere of the regiment.⁸⁵

Contemporaries disagreed about what had really happened in the Fifth LC. Smythe insisted that the charges were spurious, and members of colonial society appear to have accepted his claim (at least publicly); press coverage of Lal Mahomed's assassination attempt dismissed the trooper as 'deranged'.⁸⁶ A seditious pamphlet circulated at Secunderabad and Jaulna during this period, however, suggests how Indian military personnel may have viewed the outcome of the investigations differently. According to extracts from the pamphlet excerpted by the court of inquiry, 'An Englishman who was notorious through the world for sodomy, in proof of which there were a thousand witnesses – with the help of 24 false witnesses denied being guilty before their (the English) Court – out of regard to one of their own race, and from indulgence he was found guiltless.'⁸⁷ The text is purposefully anonymized to protect the author, making it difficult to ascertain whether it refers to Smythe. Hyder Khan, munshi of the Fifth LC, who consulted on the text while it was being composed, is reported to have said that 'parts of the work' would 'give offence if known to the European officers', to which Ghusr Beg, the munshi accused of writing the pamphlet, replied that 'as he should not make his name known nor name any particular persons, no mischief could ensue to any one.'⁸⁸ Whether the Indian population of the cantonment interpreted Smythe's acquittal as evidence of white solidarity at work is therefore plausible but unconfirmed. Lal Mahomed's family members certainly believed that Smythe was guilty. His sister, Hamida Bai, declared that Smythe's repeated harassment had pushed her brother to the point of desperation, rendering him 'careless of his life'.⁸⁹ Lal Mahomed's brother, Sheikh Ahmed, was so convinced that his sibling had been grievously wronged that he made a formal complaint on parade, even though, as he later

testified, his commanding officer warned him ‘that if I did so, he would get me hanged.’⁹⁰

As this alleged intimidation suggests, uncertainty about the case is compounded by our awareness of the inequalities that shaped these inquiries and their documentation. A havildar major testified at Smythe’s general court martial that he had witnessed a subadar in his troop accuse a sepoy of sodomy with Smythe. The havildar major swore that he had testified to this effect before a prior regimental court martial ‘but that neither the Court, nor the Conducting Officer, paid the least attention to him; and, therefore, he could not say if his evidence was recorded.’ To explain this, the havildar major speculated that ‘I think it was in the interest of all the European and Native Officers in the Regiment, to conceal the business of Sodomy which was going on.’ Smythe countered that ‘to believe this Havildar’s story, it is necessary to reject the Official documents taken at the time, and the signatures on Oath of the Subadar President, the Interpreter, and Conducting Officer’.⁹¹ For Smythe, judicial protocols made such an omission impossible. Yet, a signature on a piece of paper is not a guarantor of truth; it is precisely when documents come to stand for truth that the conditions are created for crimes of forgery and fraud, as historian Bhavani Raman has shown in the context of the colonial revenue office.⁹² Transcripts are often the best sources we have for what occurred in court, but they cannot document what was happening behind the scenes. Smythe himself argued that in advance of Watkins’s trial, Watkins tried to intimidate Smythe’s prospective witnesses by punishing a subadar and a European sergeant associated who had previously testified in Smythe’s favour during the earlier sodomy trial.⁹³ Contemporaries, then, raised the possibility that witnesses may have been ignored or else scared or threatened into silence.

The fact that the case revolved around allegations of sodomy adds an additional layer of complexity. The scandal adhered to the pattern of British nineteenth-century sodomy trials which were, in the aggregate, characterized by complex class dynamics in which the accusers were normally of lower social and economic status than the accused.⁹⁴ Their subordinate status may have made them more available for sex and vulnerable to unwanted advances, but contemporaries were always worried about the possibility of blackmail, extortion, and slander. Because sodomy was conventionally regarded as an ‘infamous’ or ‘unnatural’ crime, accusations of attempted sodomy could be seriously damaging to a man’s reputation; they were also extremely difficult to disprove. Manuals on military law commonly cited Blackstone’s principle: that ‘it is an offence of so dark a nature, so easily charged, and the negative so difficult to be proved, that the accusation should be clearly made out; for if false, it deserves a punishment inferior only to that of the crime itself.’⁹⁵ Accusations of sodomy against figures of authority were therefore often received with wariness, if not outright scepticism. As H. G. Cocks has shown in his study of sodomy prosecutions in nineteenth-century Britain, ‘common assumptions about sodomites ... tended to protect the respectable from overt suspicion’; in other words, sodomy was so closely connected with depravity in nineteenth-century discourse that contemporaries tended to argue that it would reveal itself in other ways.⁹⁶ This perhaps explains why none of Smythe’s fellow officers appear to have believed that the allegations of sodomy were true. As Watkins phrased it, ‘he could not bring himself to suppose a brother officer capable of such fearful, such diabolical conduct, as that attributed by the reports to Lieutenant-Colonel Smythe’.⁹⁷

Contemporary ideas about sodomy may have informed the case and its outcome in other ways. In the nineteenth century, sodomy was a crime regardless of consent, thereby restricting whether and how homosexual desire was expressed publicly. Lal

Mahomed's siblings claimed that their brother was harassed by Smythe, but the relationships between Smythe and other Indian soldiers under his command were described differently; one Indian officer referred to Mahomed Nasser, a rough rider, as Smythe's 'beloved'.⁹⁸ The prospect of consenting sexual relations between men was never envisaged by the British officers active in this controversy, nor the Anglo-Indian newspapers that commented on it. Still, given the incentives for remaining silent, and the penalties for speaking out, we can never be certain about the exact nature of the intimate relationships that may or may not have existed within the cantonment, nor the degree of consent that may or may not have characterized them. The particularly charged nature of sodomy trials, and the complex web of assumptions surrounding them, therefore make it extremely difficult to draw firm conclusions about what was happening in the Fifth LC.

On the surface, then, the scandal in the Fifth LC appears to raise more questions than it answers. The nature of the alleged abuses rendered the case highly emotive in a context where sodomy was classified as 'unnatural'; the fact that these acts occurred in secret made it difficult for contemporaries to ascertain the truth of what had happened. The sources that remain are sometimes conflicting; Smythe described an insidious conspiracy against him in his court martial narrative, while Watkins tried to paint a very different picture of his relationship to Yusuf Khan, as we shall see. Official records and court transcripts, meanwhile, reflected the perspectives of the military authorities who produced and archived them; questions were raised even at the time about testimony that may or may not have been left out. There is therefore much that we cannot know about events in the Fifth Light Cavalry. There are, however, certain points of consensus within the surviving evidence that can tell us something about life in the cantonment.

Making Sense of Scandal

One striking feature of the case is what it reveals about the extent of communication between the officers' bungalows and native lines. The whole trial turned on a series of conversations between a British officer and an Indian NCO. Admittedly, Watkins and Yusuf Khan had a personal history, which is how Watkins justified the sensitive nature of their conversations. 'Havildar Major Esoph Khan had been my servant from boyhood until he became a soldier when I left India in 1824,' Watkins explained. 'It will not therefore I trust excite surprise, that this man although a non commissioned officer, should have been permitted a greater latitude in conversing with me, than might be either correct, or defensible, under other circumstances.'⁹⁹ Yet, Watkins also testified to having spoken 'upon several occasions' to other Indian officers on the subject, including Jemadar Roshan Beg, a man who was 'Native Adjutant of the Regiment during the time I commanded it, and possessed my confidence',¹⁰⁰ and Jemadar Ismael Khan, who would be pensioned off at Smythe's instigation.¹⁰¹ Meanwhile, Yusuf Khan, too, was having the same conversation with other European officers, as he later testified.¹⁰² Rumours about Smythe circulated widely across the cantonment: 'they were known to every one, European and native, in the regiment.'¹⁰³

The scandal suggests that British and Indian officers were doing more than just gossiping; they were also forming factions. Both Watkins and Smythe spoke of 'parties': men united by shared agendas. According to Watkins's narrative, one of the catalysts for the investigation and subsequent court martial of E. L. Smythe was that 'a party were determined to get Colonel Smythe back to the Corps.'¹⁰⁴ Smythe, meanwhile, believed that there was a conspiracy against him, orchestrated by Watkins, but involving more than a dozen sepoys and officers. Smythe collected declarations from fifty persons who, in his words, 'voluntarily came forward to state, that they had

been tampered with by men belonging to a particular party, to induce them to join in the plot then hatching against me.’¹⁰⁵ One of the key witnesses at his trial was the quartermaster sergeant of the regiment, a European NCO who testified ‘that he was explicitly asked by a Native Officer, to join in a plan *to put down my friends*.’¹⁰⁶ The ‘friends’ referred to here were Smythe’s own supporters: the Indian officers who petitioned for his return, but also, ‘my friends at Jaulnah’, who, ‘when the business was first agitated [...] sought every information that could throw any light on it.’¹⁰⁷ By aligning themselves with Smythe, these friends, so Smythe believed, became collateral damage to Watkins’s vendetta. ‘A Havildar who had interested himself greatly on my side, was accused, by Major Watkins, of an attempt to tamper with his Witnesses; and was therefore placed in arrest’, Smythe complained.¹⁰⁸ The treatment of his Indian witnesses was one of Smythe’s primary grievances: Subadar Ahmed Khan was kept in jail four months after his acquittal, Havildar Shaik Ahmed was kept eighteen months in confinement without inquiry, and after the court martial was decided in Smythe’s favour, one of his key witnesses, Subadar Abdul Ghusur, was tried for perjury.¹⁰⁹

The support of these men helped legitimize Smythe’s cause by providing evidence of his popularity within the regiment. Contemporary press coverage on the case suggested that it was Smythe, and not Watkins, who enjoyed the support of Indian officers and sepoys, and that it was for this reason that Watkins had conjured up a scandal. *Alexander’s East India Magazine* emphasized that the catalyst for the prosecution was an *arzee* requesting Smythe’s return, at a time when Watkins was facing insubordination among his men. ‘It was against this Officer that the men memorialized, and all but mutinied, in 1831, and for one of whose Urzees ... a young soldier was flogged, merely it is stated to subdue the feeling, against the Major on the part of some men, who were anxious for the return of Colonel Smythe.’¹¹⁰ Smythe, too,

contended that ‘His [Watkins’s] object at the time when the conspiracy was concocted was to prevent my return to the Regiment, an event then much spoken of and though likely, as it was well known the Prisoner was to be superceded in a Command he had shewn himself unfit to hold.’¹¹¹ Robert Travers has demonstrated how Indian petitions were mobilized in factional disputes in mid-eighteenth-century Bengal, and the same strategies seem to apply within the armies, too; discontent among the Indian officer class reflected ill on the European officer responsible for managing them. Indian officers could therefore become active agents within the local politics of the cantonment.¹¹² Most of the native officers of the regiment appear to have been involved in the Smythe-Watkins controversy in one way or another. Subadar Mahomed Usman seems to have been the exception that proved the rule, since Major Highmoor, Watkins’s successor at the Fifth LC, supported the subadar’s request for early retirement on the grounds that ‘he has kept clear of party spirit[,] and I trust His Excellency will be pleased to consider his case in a favorable light.’¹¹³

Albert Henry Andrew Hervey, who served in the Madras Army in the 1830s, described (and condemned) this ‘party-spirit’ in his memoirs.¹¹⁴ ‘European officers,’ he complained, ‘always have their “*pet-men*” and favourites’, who ‘are constantly to be seen at their quarters, tale-bearing, lying, and slandering, to a most shameful degree; shameful not only in the individual guilty of such mean conduct, but doubly so in the officer encouraging it.’¹¹⁵ While in theory Indian officers were responsible for apprising their commanding officer of goings-on in the native lines, Hervey felt that this practice, if pursued too zealously, could produce ‘all manner of heart-burnings, bickerings, false reports, and disputes’.¹¹⁶ Hervey discouraged his military readers from forming personal affinities that might bias them in favour of specific individuals, emphasizing the danger of allowing Indian officers to exercise undue influence. ‘Is it not the case in nine out of

ten, when promotions are required to be made, that the company officers sends for *his* native officer and consults him',¹¹⁷ Hervey asked, and 'how many an undeserving man obtains his promotion by the partiality and favouritism of the officer, or of those in whom that officer places so much undue confidence?'¹¹⁸ An anonymous soldier, writing to the *Calcutta Journal*, agreed that 'when a Native Officer was to be selected from each corps, for promotion as Subadar-Major [...] there were men to advocate the supercession of six or seven *unexceptionable* Officers for the aggrandizement of a *pet*.'¹¹⁹

The derogatory term 'pet' belies the fact that vertical relationships prevailed throughout the army, as in most domains of nineteenth-century life. As historian Harold Perkin noted, 'the relationship of patronage was the module of which the social structure was built.'¹²⁰ European officers relied on the information and support that Indian officers could provide. Meanwhile, because so many of the vicissitudes of military life depended on character references and recommendations, Indian officers had good reason to try to curry favour with European officers. Through the intercession of a friendly officer, one could secure preferential treatment and the occasional favour, useful when seeking permission to go on furlough, for example. While promotion within the Company's armies was supposed to occur according to principles of strict seniority, a bad reputation was considered sufficient cause for breaking with this convention; career advancement therefore depended on the goodwill of one's officers.¹²¹ Finally, the support of a European officer could become critical in moments of crisis. Historians have demonstrated the importance of discretion within the British military justice system, showing that the bad soldier or 'old offender' was punished with harsh sentences, whereas soldiers capable of obtaining good testimonials were

more likely to be treated mercifully.¹²² The patronage of senior officers therefore acted as insurance against adversity as well as a mechanism for advancement.

Unwittingly, this exchange of favours could connect Indian soldiers to European officers in problematic ways. As evidence that Smythe's mind was 'warped' and 'judgement blinded' by his outrage at the sodomy charges, Watkins pointed out that 'he swore, that from his knowledge of the character of Jemadar Fyze Uddeen he did not believe him worthy of credence, even on his oath; and yet this native officer was promoted by the recommendation of Lieutenant Colonel Smythe, and possesses a written testimonial under that officers signature that he had always borne the highest character.'¹²³ Smythe, in turn, complained that two of his accusers had come to him for character references. For Smythe, this stank of hypocrisy: 'this man [Yusuf Khan] asked me for a written character whilst his mouth was yet reeking with the beastiality of his communications'. Yusuf Khan had once assisted Smythe after the colonel fell off his horse, so when he learned that Smythe was leaving the regiment, the havildar major approached him to ask for a recommendation for promotion, which he received, along with several pieces of nankeen (a cotton fabric commonly used for making trousers). Watkins was aware that Yusuf Khan had been given this reference, and for Smythe, this should have alerted Watkins to Yusuf Khan's deceit: 'if this informant believed what he had so often repeated as current rumours in the Regiment surely I was the last person he as an honest Man should have gone to for a character'.¹²⁴ Yet, Yusuf Khan's personal opinion of Smythe was irrelevant in this context. Whatever Yusuf Khan thought about the allegations of sodomy, he had little choice but to cultivate Smythe's good opinion if he wanted to advance in the service; his actions were predetermined by the army's hierarchical structures.

Smythe might have condemned Yusuf Khan as a hypocrite, but ultimately it was Major John Watkins, not Yusuf Khan, who was discharged from the service. Smythe wrote to the adjutant general to formally request Yusuf Khan's dismissal along with a number of other Indian officers and NCOs, but did not prosecute, apparently because he was tired of airing his personal life in court and felt that to appear again as a prosecutor would be both 'degrading as well as annoying.'¹²⁵ Punishing Watkins was the real priority; as Smythe put it in a letter to the adjutant general shortly after his acquittal, 'The voice of the Army seems to demand it from me: and I have been assured, by persons of judgment and experience, that my character will suffer, were I to shrink from the task'.¹²⁶ For Smythe, his acquittal would not be complete until he had proven the existence of the conspiracy that had given rise to the rumour in the first place. Watkins was, in Smythe's mind, 'the individual who, by his secret machinations, encouraged and fostered vague and unfounded reports into specific Charges of Infamy', the one 'who is identified by every one with my base accusers – if not as their instigator, at least as their protector.'¹²⁷ Smythe campaigned long and hard to bring Watkins to trial, even publishing a pamphlet on the case which excerpted his correspondence with government in an attempt to publicly embarrass them into acceding to his demands.

Watkins's senior rank increased his culpability in Smythe's eyes. Smythe argued that the only reason that Yusuf Khan continued to revert to the allegations of sodomy was because he saw that it pleased his commanding officer, whom he had good reason to want to ingratiate. As Smythe put it, 'by complacent listening, [Watkins] induc[ed] the supposition that he would joyfully learn their reality and truth.'¹²⁸ In the process, Smythe declared that 'his [Watkins's] listening to the Havildar gave strength to the rumours, he [Yusuf Khan] himself was disseminating whilst he was reporting his mere hearing them; that it encouraged others to join with him, seeing he had the countenance

of the Commanding Officer ready to listen to any thing'.¹²⁹ Both Yusuf Khan and Watkins were, in their different ways, guilty of subverting military discipline by gossiping about their commander; yet, Watkins's authority within the regiment meant that his participation in this gossip helped legitimize and encourage it in a way that Yusuf Khan, on his own, could not have done.

Perhaps just as importantly, however, Watkins was also held accountable as a gentleman. The conversations represented, in Smythe's mind, a 'violation of the Principles of right between man and man and of the ordinary rules of acting between Gentlemen'.¹³⁰ Watkins's status as a gentleman meant that he was subject to social conventions that Yusuf Khan was not, including, to quote military historian Edward Spiers, 'requirements of dress and deportment, an emphasis on honour and integrity, and a conformity with the manners and etiquette of polite society.'¹³¹ Watkins's scandalous and infamous conduct consisted, not simply in encouraging the circulation of rumours about his commanding officer, but in betraying his friend and host. The formal charges specified that at the time of the conversations Watkins and Smythe had been 'living on apparent terms of intimacy and friendship'.¹³² Smythe made much of the fact that around the time when at least one of these conversations was said to have taken place, Watkins had been his guest, and had dined at his home. At the end of this period, Smythe had presented Watkins with a snuff box as a token of their 'good feelings towards each other', which Watkins accepted; it was this 'simulation of friendship' that transformed Watkins's conduct from a dereliction of duty into a betrayal.¹³³

Perhaps surprisingly, this dimension of the case appears to have eclipsed the question of military discipline; the friendship between the two men dominated the trial itself as well as press coverage of it. Both men summoned witnesses to testify to the degree of intimacy existing between them. Captain Daniel Alexander Fenning, witness

for the defence, testified that ‘Lieutenant Colonel Smythe was on greater terms of intimacy with several other Officers of the Regiment’, while Lieutenant Alexander Macleod, witness for the prosecution, asserted that although Smythe was generally liked, it was ‘remarked that the Prisoner was a great deal with him.’¹³⁴ Macleod had to endure a series of questions about Watkins’s breakfasting habits: whether he breakfasted at the mess, how often he breakfasted with Smythe relative to other officers, whether he might have breakfasted with other officers without Macleod’s knowledge.¹³⁵ The snuff box was mentioned repeatedly; the court were curious to know whether the box had been seen in Watkins’s possession, and if so, if it bore any inscription.¹³⁶ Meanwhile, the Anglo-Indian press made much of Watkins’s treachery. The salient point, as the *Bombay Gazette* interpreted it, was that Watkins was ‘accused of suborning evidence against him, while living upon terms of intimacy with the Colonel.’¹³⁷ *Alexander’s East India Magazine* also identified this as Watkins’s primary offence: that ‘Major Watkins who always professed himself a friend to Col. Smythe, resided at his house, partook of his hospitality was the very individual employed in the laudable work of collecting and arranging the filthy evidence against the Colonel.’¹³⁸ Watkins was keen to demonstrate that he owed no special obligation to Smythe, that the ‘intimacy & Friendship’ that existed between them was no more nor less ‘than that which usually subsists between Brother Officers’, but he does not seem to have succeeded in persuading his audience.¹³⁹

In addition to trying (unsuccessfully) to downplay the debt of friendship owed to Smythe, Watkins also tried to portray his friendship with Yusuf Khan in the proper light. The prosecution depicted the relationship in insidious terms; Smythe described Yusuf Khan as Watkins’s ‘confidential man’, his agent within the native lines.¹⁴⁰ Watkins, by contrast, was concerned to place the conversations in context, and, in so

doing, to convince the court that, far from evidencing an underhanded plot, the gossip was just one instance of harmless small talk between two people who had known each other a long time and were in the habit of chatting informally. Watkins emphasized that he had known Yusuf Khan since the havildar major was a boy, and that ‘when the man came to my house as is the common custom with native soldiers I was accustomed to ask after his welfare and perhaps inquire the news of the day’; it was in this context, he repeated, that rumours about Smythe surfaced.¹⁴¹ In his trial, Watkins argued that it would have been wrong ‘to bring the man to punishment for merely mentioning that a rumour had been current’.¹⁴² In his pamphlet, Watkins went further, arguing that to do so would have been ‘a dishonourable breach of friendship’.¹⁴³

For Watkins, such a breach of friendship would have had serious implications for discipline and esprit de corps within the army. As part of his appeal to the court of directors, Watkins invoked broader discourses about the attenuation of the bonds of loyalty between sepoys and officers to emphasize the injustice of his dismissal. For, Watkins observed, ‘unrestrained and familiar intercourse with the native soldier is inculcated as a duty, and enforced by reiterated orders, on the officers of the Indian army’, and yet, ‘will the fate your memorialist’s attempt to treat a native as a friend has drawn on him, be an incentive to others to seek their intimacy? Will it not render all the orders which have been issued on the subject worse than useless?’¹⁴⁴ Watkins viewed his own case as a powerful demonstration of the illegibility of the EIC’s codes, which explicitly instructed officers to treat their men like friends, but which permitted Smythe and others like him to prosecute a fellow officer precisely for fulfilling this duty. Watkins argued that his trial would be regarded within the army as a cautionary tale of the dangers of treating Indian officers and sepoys like friends.

The trial of John Watkins was thus, in many ways, a disagreement about friendship; what counted as friendship, and what kinds of friendship weighed heaviest in the scale of priorities. Watkins himself argued that his friendship with Yusuf Khan mattered. Watkins had known Yusuf Khan for decades whereas his acquaintance with Smythe was comparatively brief; moreover, Watkins believed that part of his responsibility as an officer in the native cavalry was to conciliate the men under his command through friendly behaviour, which included the exchange of news that might touch on the reputations of senior officers; as he put it, ‘confidence between the native and his immediate superior, must, to answer any good end, be unreserved.’¹⁴⁵ Social historians have established the importance of gossip for establishing and consolidating bonds with friends, neighbours, and patrons; in the EIC’s armies, gossip had the added advantage of keeping officers apprised of the mood in camp.¹⁴⁶ To keep these lines of communication open, Watkins argued, he had to maintain the trust of his officers; to have reported Yusuf Khan would have resulted in ‘the rupture of all future confidence in the native towards the European.’¹⁴⁷ Smythe, by contrast, emphasized the importance of the exchange of services; because of gifts of food and snuffboxes in Watkins’s case, or fabrics and character references in Yusuf Khan’s, Smythe believed that both men were obligated to him, and that these obligations outweighed their personal loyalties to one another. Whereas Watkins argued that to report Yusuf Khan would have been the more serious breach of friendship, Smythe contended that Watkins’s primary obligation was to his host and commanding officer. Contemporary press coverage of the case, combined with the outcome of the trial, suggests that Smythe’s interpretation was shared by many of his counterparts. Such an interpretation favoured those who were able to grant favours in the first place, thus consolidating hierarchies of race and rank within the army. Yet, as Watkins’s petition clearly demonstrates, it was possible for an

officer to argue that he owed something to the Indian soldiers under his command as well as to the British gentlemen with whom he breakfasted and exchanged gifts.

The scandal in the Fifth LC is just one story among many that might be told about the EIC's armies; still, although it cannot capture the full spectrum of relationships that may have existed between European and Indian officers and NCOs, it does point to some fundamental contradictions underlying life in the EIC's armies. Other officers echoed Watkins's concerns. One particularly vocal critic was Captain William White, Bengal Army, who lost his staff position in 1821 for forwarding the complaints of two Indian officers who had been injured in a hunting accident when a European surgeon carelessly shot a waterfowl in the vicinity of their huts. Decades after the events in question, White continued to insist that he had been a victim of the Company's inability to abide by its own codes. It was his conviction that at all points in the affair he had acted 'in strict conformity and obedience to the mutiny act, and articles of war.'¹⁴⁸ 'In receiving their complaint, and transferring it to the Magistrate just as it was handed to me in writing, without a single comment of my own [...] I scarcely did my naked duty', White insisted.¹⁴⁹ When the magistrate appeared not to take their complaints seriously, White had an obligation, as he saw it, 'to protect my officers', and 'this I did by reporting to the Government, and also to the Commander-in-chief, the shameless course of proceedings which had been carried on.'¹⁵⁰ He had no idea that, in so doing, he was putting himself at risk of reprimand: 'It had never been suggested to my mind, even as a bare possibility, that the part which I had taken, in affording just protection to the officers under my command [...] could have subjected me to the displeasure of his Excellency.'¹⁵¹ Referring again to the Mutiny Act, White asked whether, 'with these laws and penalties before me – was it possible to contemplate such an issue?'.¹⁵² The Bengal Army was thus guilty of what philosophers Havi Carel and

Ian James Kidd have described as ‘institutional opacity’: ‘a general tendency within large-scale and internally complex institutions to increasingly become resistant to forms of assessment and understanding.’¹⁵³ In White’s mind, he had been punished for accepting the Bengal Army’s avowed principles at face value. Later, in a printed letter addressed to Prime Minister William Lamb, Viscount Melbourne, White commented wryly on the 1831 parliamentary inquiry, wherein expert witnesses lamented that ‘the bond of attachment between the Native and European officers is almost broken’. For White, the findings were bittersweet. As he put it, ‘I was the first and last officer that ever dared venture to make an appeal to England against any of the many thousands of cases of oppression to which the Native troops have been exposed. The result of that appeal is well known to the whole Indian army; it was published to every regiment. They never have forgotten it; and what is more, my Lord, they never will.’¹⁵⁴

Unbeknownst to White, members of the EIC’s executive privately shared his opinion. A memorandum on the case issuing from the Military Secretary’s office conceded that ‘as a general principle it must be distinctly admitted that a European officer is bound to pay paramount attention to the complaints of the natives placed under his command; and that an obvious leaning towards his men in preference to a disposition in favour of the European who is alleged to have injured them, ought to be met by the Government with tokens of warm approbation rather than marks of censure.’¹⁵⁵ The memorandum nevertheless agreed with the commander in chief insofar as it admitted ‘that an officer ceases to be the friend of his men’ if he takes at face value a complaint that ‘implies more of malice than of real injury,’ and that in such a case his responsibility was to ‘soothe the irritated feelings of the complainants.’¹⁵⁶ Yet, how could a commanding officer be certain that a complaint was exaggerated? Who, in this instance, deserved the benefit of the doubt: the men for whom he was responsible, or his

fellow officers, to whose gentlemanly society he belonged? What it meant to be a friend, and to whom one owed one's friendship, was far from obvious. These uncertainties could have profound personal and professional consequences, as both John Watkins and William White could attest.

Conclusion

Within the existing literature on the EIC's armies, British officers and Indian soldiers are assumed to have led largely separate lives. The scandal in the Fifth LC, in contrast, shows just how entangled their fates could become. These friendships could be mutually beneficial; Indian officers and NCOs provided their European commanding officers with information and legitimacy, while European officers could procure favours and facilitate professional advancement. These relationships, however, could also become complicated; obligations could pull in different directions, factions could emerge, and problems could ensue. British officers identified strongly as gentlemen and were expected to adhere to the conventions of gentlemanly society, but what if these precepts ran counter to the paternalistic officer ideal, or the EIC's injunctions to conciliate Indian officers? Watkins had a choice: to report Yusuf Khan's gossip to his friend and erstwhile commanding officer, or to treat the conversation as confidential.

Contemporaries regarded his silence as treacherous; for Watkins, the greater risk was that he would lose the trust of his men, without which he could not maintain his personal authority within the regiment. These differing perspectives on the case reflected a fundamental ambivalence at the heart of the EIC's armies as institutions which relied on the military labour of Indians but were predicated on racial hierarchies.

Watkins was not alone in his concerns about loyalty and esprit de corps within the EIC's armies; the 1857 Uprising sharpened concerns that had already been growing

within the army for some time. Though 'native' soldiers continued to dominate the armed forces in India, the proportion of European men was increased, in hopes of mitigating the colonial government's dependence on its colonized subjects. Still, debates around Indian officers did not disappear. Though the events of 1857 were seen as evidence that Indian officers had failed in their duty as channels of information, the conclusion that some officers drew was that Indian officers needed to be invested with more authority rather than less, especially given that the irregular corps of cavalry, where the proportion of British officers was lower and Indian officers commanded their own companies and squadrons, had largely remained loyal. The debate about what to do with Indian officers rumbled on into the twentieth century, where it acquired new urgency in a context of rising nationalism. Responding to calls for the removal of racial restrictions, a process of 'Indianization' occurred over the course of 1929-31 whereby Indians were able to enter the army as cadets and be trained as officers.¹⁵⁷ By the 1940s, the composition of the officer corps had been fundamentally altered, with significant consequences for the intertwined processes of Indian independence and Partition, as Kate Imy has shown.¹⁵⁸

Historians have uncovered much about the experience of Indian soldiers during this period of change from the late nineteenth to the twentieth century.¹⁵⁹ The experiences of World War I have furnished us with particularly poignant source material, as Santanu Das highlighted.¹⁶⁰ Yet, despite the highly militarized character of the nineteenth-century British empire, and the importance of India as its so-called garrison in the east, we still know so little about social life within the Indian cantonment during this earlier period. The objective of this article has been to redirect our attention to this longer history, to demonstrate the value of the cantonment as a worthwhile site for the study of cross-cultural encounters, and to emphasize the importance of Indian

officers and NCOs as liminal figures whose ordeals can tell us much about how the boundaries of race and rank were negotiated in imperial contexts. Combining official records and cheap pamphlets, we can discern the alliances that took shape between Europeans and Indians, the motives that informed them, and the forces to which they succumbed. In so doing, we can begin to identify the distinctive features of military encounters, framed, as they were, by a separate set of laws and conventions. Understanding these interactions is important, because by putting military camps and cantonments at the centre of study, we reflect not only the preoccupations of British officialdom, but also the experiences of many thousands of Indians whose main point of contact with the EIC was the army.

¹ Watkins, *To the Honorable the Chairman*, xxx.

² Gilbert, 'Law and Honour Among Eighteenth-Century British Army Officers', 78.

³ Watkins, *To the Honorable the Chairman*, xlv.

⁴ Perkin, *The Origins of Modern English Society 1780-1880*, 46.

⁵ Tadmor, *Family and Friends in Eighteenth-Century England*, 213.

⁶ Omissi, *The Sepoy and the Raj*, 3.

⁷ Villiers, *Report from the Select Committee*, V, xxx.

⁸ Stocqueler, *The Hand-Book of India*, 101.

⁹ 'The Indian Army', 565.

¹⁰ Alavi, *The Sepoys and the Company*; Peers, "'The Habitual Nobility of Being'", 545-569.

¹¹ Welsch, *The Company's Sword*, 6.

¹² Peers, "'The Habitual Nobility of Being,'" 552.

¹³ Peers, *Between Mars and Mammon*, 85. See also Omissi, *The Sepoy and the Raj*, 156.

¹⁴ Stoler, *Carnal Knowledge and Imperial Power*, 12.

¹⁵ Jackson, 'The Private Lives of Empire', 2.

-
- ¹⁶ Gandhi, *Affective Communities*.
- ¹⁷ See note 5.
- ¹⁸ Stoler, 'Tense and Tender Ties,' 831.
- ¹⁹ Ghosh, *Sex and the Family in Colonial India*, 206-45; Wald, *Vice in the Barracks*, 24-44; Ballhatchet, *Race, Sex and Class under the Raj*.
- ²⁰ Myerly, *British Military Spectacle*, 11.
- ²¹ Bevan, *Thirty Years in India*, I, 89.
- ²² Arnold, 'Race, Place and Bodily Difference in Early Nineteenth-Century India', 262.
- ²³ Kolsky, *Colonial Justice in British India*, 22.
- ²⁴ Cochrane, *Regulations Applicable to the European Officer in India*, 1095.
- ²⁵ Heathcote, *The Military in British India*, 46. Alavi, *The Sepoys and the Company*, 45 describes the operation of recruiting stations in North India, but the testimony of expert witnesses by the parliamentary select committee of 1831-2 suggests that recruitment operated primarily through personal networks. See for example 'Minutes of Evidence,' in Hyde Villiers, *Report of the Select Committee*, V, 16.
- ²⁶ Phrythian-Adams, *Madras Soldier*, 132-38.
- ²⁷ Wickremesekera, 'Best Black Troops in the World', 128-9; Alavi, *The Sepoy and the Company*, 43.
- ²⁸ Fisher, *A Clash of Cultures*, 185.
- ²⁹ Ramusack, *The Indian Princes and their States*, 48-50.
- ³⁰ Wickremesekera, 'Best Black Troops', 114.
- ³¹ 'The Indian Army', 572.
- ³² Malcolm, *The Political History of India from 1784 to 1823*, II, 233.
- ³³ Bevan, *Thirty Years*, 91.
- ³⁴ Peers, "'The Habitual Nobility of Being'", 552.
- ³⁵ Peers, 'Imperial Vice', 28; 30.
- ³⁶ Cowell, 'The Kaccha-Pakka Divide', para. 24.
- ³⁷ Peers, 'Imperial Vice', 32.

-
- ³⁸ Welsch, *The Company's Sword*, 6.
- ³⁹ Wickremesekera, 'Best Black Troops', 166-8.
- ⁴⁰ 'Considerations on the Present State of the Native Army by an Indian Officer', 67.
- ⁴¹ 'Minutes of Evidence' in Villiers, *Select Committee Report*, V, 1.
- ⁴² *Ibid.*, 155.
- ⁴³ *Ibid.*, 165.
- ⁴⁴ Alavi, *The Company and the Raj*, 90-91.
- ⁴⁵ Peers, 'That Habitual Nobility of Being', 547.
- ⁴⁶ Caulfield, *Observations on our Indian Administration*, 117-118.
- ⁴⁷ Cochrane, *Regulations Applicable to the European Officer in India*, 199-200.
- ⁴⁸ Badenach, *Inquiry into the State of the Indian Army*, 105. On theories of oriental despotism, see Marshall, 'Taming the Exotic', 56.
- ⁴⁹ Adam White, *Considerations on the State of British India* (London: J. M. Richardson, 1822), p. 353.
- ⁵⁰ A Madras Officer, 'Native Army of the Coast', 33-34.
- ⁵¹ Carnaticus, 'General View of our Indian Army', 275.
- ⁵² Bevan, *Thirty Years*, 91.
- ⁵³ Papers regarding a seditious pamphlet, 19-20.
- ⁵⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 66-74.
- ⁵⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 60.
- ⁵⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 61.
- ⁵⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 60-61.
- ⁵⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 62.
- ⁵⁹ Gilbert, 'Law and Honour Among Eighteenth-Century British Army Officers', 76.
- ⁶⁰ *Ibid.*, 75.
- ⁶¹ James, *A Collection of the Charges, Opinions, and Sentences of General Courts Martial, as Published by Authority*, 37; 234; 238; 250; 316; 337; 368; 369; 375; 392; 405; 511; 516; 519; 584; 729.

-
- ⁶² Hough, *The Practice of Courts-Martial*, 22–29.
- ⁶³ Adam White, *Considerations on the State of British India*, 356.
- ⁶⁴ Alryyes, ‘War at a Distance’, 532.
- ⁶⁵ For this paragraph, see Watkins, *To the Honorable the Chairman*, p. i-ii.
- ⁶⁶ ‘The second rank of native officer in a company of sepoy’. Yule, *Hobson-Jobson*, 459.
- ⁶⁷ A subadar is the first rank of native officer in a company of sepoy. *Ibid.*
- ⁶⁸ ‘Military Courts-Martial in India’, 597.
- ⁶⁹ For this paragraph, see Watkins, *To the Honorable the Chairman*, iv; The European General Court Martial of Major John Watkins, f. 239-40.
- ⁷⁰ Smythe, *Two Letters*, 1-2.
- ⁷¹ Harvey, ‘Prosecutions for Sodomy in England at the Beginning of the Nineteenth Century’, 941; Cocks, *Nameless Offences*, 32.
- ⁷² Smythe, *Two Letters*, 31.
- ⁷³ ‘Court Martial’, 5.
- ⁷⁴ European General Court Martial of Major John Watkins, f. 214.
- ⁷⁵ Case of Lieut. Col. E. L. Smythe of the Cavalry, 19.
- ⁷⁶ *Ibid.*, 21.
- ⁷⁷ *Ibid.*
- ⁷⁸ *Ibid.*, 22.
- ⁷⁹ *Ibid.*, 59.
- ⁸⁰ *Ibid.*
- ⁸¹ *Ibid.*, 65; 67.
- ⁸² Watkins, *To the Honorable the Chairman*, xli.
- ⁸³ *Ibid.*, xxxvi.
- ⁸⁴ *Ibid.*, viii.
- ⁸⁵ *Ibid.*, xxxviii.
- ⁸⁶ ‘Asiatic Intelligence – Madras’, 610.
- ⁸⁷ Papers regarding a seditious pamphlet, 76.

-
- ⁸⁸ Ibid., 45-46.
- ⁸⁹ Watkins, *To the Honorable the Chairman*, 12.
- ⁹⁰ Ibid., 20.
- ⁹¹ Smythe, *Two Letters*, 2-3.
- ⁹² Raman, *Document Raj*, 3.
- ⁹³ Smythe, *Two Letters*, iv; 4.
- ⁹⁴ Upchurch, *Before Wilde*, 95-6.
- ⁹⁵ Hough, *Precedents in Military Law*, 467; Kennedy, *Practical Remarks on the Proceedings of General Courts Martial*, 201.
- ⁹⁶ Cocks, *Nameless Offences*, 118-19.
- ⁹⁷ Watkins, *To the Honorable the Chairman*, x.
- ⁹⁸ European General Court Martial of Major John Watkins, f. 252.
- ⁹⁹ Ibid., f. 239.
- ¹⁰⁰ Ibid., f. 223.
- ¹⁰¹ Ibid., f. 224.
- ¹⁰² Ibid., f. 230.
- ¹⁰³ Watkins, *To the Honorable the Chairman*, p. xlv.
- ¹⁰⁴ European General Court Martial of Major John Watkins, f. 239.
- ¹⁰⁵ Smythe, *Two Letters*, iii.
- ¹⁰⁶ Ibid., iv.
- ¹⁰⁷ Ibid., 3.
- ¹⁰⁸ Ibid.
- ¹⁰⁹ Ibid., 33.
- ¹¹⁰ 'Military Courts-Martial in India', 508.
- ¹¹¹ European General Court Martial of Major John Watkins, f. 250.
- ¹¹² Travers, 'Indian Petitioning and Colonial State-Formation in Eighteenth-Century Bengal', 107.
- ¹¹³ Case of Lieut. Col. E.L. Smythe of the Cavalry, 70.

-
- ¹¹⁴ Hervey, *Ten Years in India*, I, 145.
- ¹¹⁵ *Ibid.*, 144.
- ¹¹⁶ *Ibid.*, 145.
- ¹¹⁷ *Ibid.*, 146.
- ¹¹⁸ *Ibid.*, 148.
- ¹¹⁹ A Soldier, 'A Soldier's Story', 242-243.
- ¹²⁰ Perkin, *The Origins of Modern English Society*, 50.
- ¹²¹ Villiers, *Report from the Select Committee*, 13.
- ¹²² Stepler, 'British Military Law, Discipline, and the Conduct of Regimental Courts Martial in the Later Eighteenth Century', 878.
- ¹²³ European General Court Martial of Major John Watkins, f. 242.
- ¹²⁴ *Ibid.*, f. 215-216.
- ¹²⁵ Case of Lieut. Col. E. L. Smythe of the Cavalry, 27.
- ¹²⁶ Smythe, *Two Letters*, 16.
- ¹²⁷ *Ibid.*, 22.
- ¹²⁸ European General Court Martial of Major John Watkins, f. 220.
- ¹²⁹ *Ibid.*, f. 253.
- ¹³⁰ *Ibid.*, f. 221.
- ¹³¹ Spiers, *The Army and Society*, 1.
- ¹³² European General Court Martial of Major John Watkins, f. 214.
- ¹³³ *Ibid.*, f. 221-222.
- ¹³⁴ *Ibid.*, f. 231; f. 225.
- ¹³⁵ *Ibid.*, f. 226-227.
- ¹³⁶ *Ibid.*, f. 227.
- ¹³⁷ Editorial, *Bombay Gazette*, 2.
- ¹³⁸ 'Military Courts-Martial in India', 508.
- ¹³⁹ European General Court Martial of Major John Watkins, f. 226.
- ¹⁴⁰ *Ibid.*, f. 216.

-
- ¹⁴¹ Ibid., f. 239.
- ¹⁴² Ibid., f. 239.
- ¹⁴³ Watkins, *To the Honorable the Chairman*, xlv.
- ¹⁴⁴ Ibid., xlv.
- ¹⁴⁵ Ibid.
- ¹⁴⁶ Walker, 'Whispering Fama', 23.
- ¹⁴⁷ Watkins, *To the Honorable the Chairman*, xlv.
- ¹⁴⁸ White, *Petition of Capt. William White*, 19.
- ¹⁴⁹ Ibid., 79.
- ¹⁵⁰ Ibid., 83.
- ¹⁵¹ White, *A Letter Addressed to the Proprietors of India Stock*, 76.
- ¹⁵² Ibid., 81.
- ¹⁵³ Carel and Kidd, 'Institutional Opacity, Epistemic Vulnerability, and Institutional Testimonial Justice', 481.
- ¹⁵⁴ White, *Mirzas Kaiwan Jah*, 107-108.
- ¹⁵⁵ IOR/L/MIL/5/393 coll 153a, 347.
- ¹⁵⁶ Ibid.
- ¹⁵⁷ For this paragraph, see Omissi, *Sepoy and the Raj*, 157-8; 189-91.
- ¹⁵⁸ Imy, *Faithful Fighters*.
- ¹⁵⁹ In addition to other texts cited in this article, see for example Barkawi, *Soldiers of Empire*.
- ¹⁶⁰ Das, *India, Empire and First World War Culture*.

Bibliography

- A Madras Officer. 'Native Army of the Coast'. *Calcutta Journal* 1, no. 3 (3 January 1822): 33–35.
- Alavi, Seema. *The Sepoys and the Company: Tradition and Transition in Northern India 1770-1830*. Delhi: Oxford University Press, 1995.
- Alryyes, Ala. 'War at a Distance: Court-Martial Narratives in the Eighteenth Century'. *Eighteenth-Century Studies* 41, no. 4 (2008): 525–42.
- 'Asiatic Intelligence - Madras', *Asiatic Journal and Monthly Register for British India and its Dependencies* 24 (1827): 608.
- Arnold, David. 'Race, Place and Bodily Difference in Early Nineteenth-Century India'. *Historical Research* 77, no. 196 (1 May 2004): 254–73.
- Badenach, Walter. *Inquiry into the State of the Indian Army, with Suggestions for Its Improvement, and the Establishment of a Military Police for India*. London: John Murray, 1826.
- Barkawi, Tarak. *Soldiers of Empire: Indian and British Armies in World War II*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2017.
- Bevan, Major H. *Thirty Years in India: Or, A Soldier's Reminiscences of Native and European Life in the Presidencies, from 1808 to 1838*. Vol. 1. London: Pelham Richardson, 1839.
- Case of Lieut. Col. E. L. Smythe of the Cavalry, Board's Collections, IOR/F/4/1631/65326, Asia, Pacific and Africa Collections, British Library, London.
- Carel, Havi, and Ian James Kidd. 'Institutional Opacity, Epistemic Vulnerability, and Institutional Testimonial Justice'. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies* 29, no. 4 (8 August 2021): 473–96.
- Carnaticus. 'General View of Our Indian Army'. *Calcutta Journal* 5, no. 256 (26 September 1821): 273–76.
- Caulfield, Lieut.-Colonel James. *Observations on Our Indian Administration, Civil and Military*. London: Smith, Elder, and Co Cornhill, 1832.
- Cochrane, George E. *Regulations Applicable to the European Officer in India*. 2nd ed. London: Harrison & Sons, 1867.
- Cocks, H. G. *Nameless Offences: Speaking of Male Homosexual Desire in Nineteenth-Century England*. London: I. B. Tauris, 2003.
- 'Considerations on the Present State of the Native Army by an Indian Officer', *Oriental Herald* 6, no. 19 (1825): 67.
- 'Court Martial'. *Naval & Military Gazette and Weekly Chronicle of the United Service*. 28 February 1835.
- Cowell, Christopher. 'The Kaccha-Pakka Divide: Material, Space and Architecture in the Military Cantonments of British India (1765-1889)'. *ABE Journal* 9–10 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.4000/abe.10893>.
- Das, Santanu. *India, Empire, and First World War Culture: Writings, Images, and Songs*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2018.
- 'Editorial'. *Bombay Gazette*. 17 January 1835.
- European General Court Martial of Major John Watkins, Records of the Military Department, IOR/L/MIL/5, Asia, Pacific and Africa Collections, British Library, London.
- Fisher, Michael H. *A Clash of Cultures: Awadh, The British, and the Mughals*. New Delhi: Manohar, 1987.

- Gandhi, Leela. *Affective Communities: Anticolonial Thought, Fin-de-Siècle Radicalism, and the Politics of Friendship*. Durham, NC: Duke University Press, 2006.
- Ghosh, Durba. *Sex and the Family in Colonial India: The Making of Empire*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2006.
- Gilbert, Arthur N. 'Law and Honour Among Eighteenth-Century British Army Officers'. *The Historical Journal* 19, no. 1 (1976): 75–87.
- Harvey, A. D. 'Prosecutions for Sodomy in England at the Beginning of the Nineteenth Century'. *The Historical Journal* 21, no. 4 (1978): 939–48.
- Heathcote, T. A. *The Military in British India: The Development of British Land Forces in South Asia, 1600-1947*. Barnsley: Praetorian Press, repr. 2013.
- Hervey, Albert Henry Andrew. *Ten Years in India: Or, The Life of a Young Officer*. Vol. 1. London: W. Shoberl, 1850.
- Hough, William. *Precedents in Military Law: Including the Practice of Courts Martial, the Mode of Conducting Trials, the Duties of Officers at Military Courts of Inquests, Courts of Inquiry, Courts of Requests, Etc. Etc.* London: W. H. Allen, 1855.
- Hough, William. *The Practice of Courts-Martial. Second*, 2nd ed. London: Kingsbury, Parbury and Allen, 1825.
- Imy, Kate. *Faithful Fighters: Identity and Power in the British Indian Army*. Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2019.
- Jackson, Will. 'The Private Lives of Empire: Emotion, Intimacy, and Colonial Rule'. *Itinerario* 42, no. 1 (April 2018): 1–15.
- James, Charles. *A Collection of the Charges, Opinions, and Sentences of General Courts Martial, as Published by Authority; from the Year 1795 to the Present Time; Intended to Serve as an Appendix to Tytler's Treatise on Military Law, and Forming a Book of Cases and References; with a Copious Index*. London: T. Egerton, 1820.
- Kennedy, Vans. *Practical Remarks on the Proceedings of General Courts Martial*. London: A. Strahan, 1825.
- Kolsky, Elizabeth. *Colonial Justice in British India*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2010.
- Malcolm, John. *The Political History of India from 1784 to 1823*. Vol. 2. London: John Murray, 1826.
- 'Military Courts-Martial in India'. *Alexander's East India and Colonial Magazine* 8, no. 48 (1834).
- Myerly, Scott Hughes. *British Military Spectacle: From the Napoleonic Wars through the Crimea*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1996.
- Omissi, David. *The Sepoy and the Raj: The Indian Army, 1860-1940*. Houndmills: Macmillan Press, 1994.
- Papers regarding a seditious pamphlet written in Hindustani by a munshi of the 28th Madras Native Infantry and distributed to the Muslim inhabitants of Secunderabad, Board's Collections, IOR/F/4/1550/62018, Asia, Pacific, and Africa Collections, British Library, London.
- Peers, Douglas. *Between Mars and Mammon: Colonial Armies and the Garrison State in India 1819-1835*. London: Tauris Academic Studies, 1995.
- Peers, Douglas. "'The Habitual Nobility of Being': British Officers and the Social Construction of the Bengal Army in the Early Nineteenth Century". *Modern Asian Studies* 25, no. 3 (1991): 545–69.
- Peers, Douglas. 'Imperial Vice: Sex, Drink and the Health of British Troops in North Indian Cantonments, 1800-1858.' In *Guardians of Empire: The Armed Forces of*

- the Colonial Powers c. 1700-1964*. Edited by David Killingray and David Omissi. Manchester: Manchester University Press, 1999.
- Perkin, Harold. *The Origins of Modern English Society 1780-1880*. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul, 1969.
- Phrythian-Adams, E. G. *Madras Soldier*. Madras: Government Press, 1948.
- Raman, Bhavani. *Document Raj: Writings and Scribes in Early Colonial South India*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2012.
- Ramusack, Barbara N. *The Indian Princes and Their States*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2004.
- Smythe, E.L. *Two Letters of Appeal ... Addressed by Lieut.-Colonel E.L. Smythe, of the Eighth Regiment of Madras Light Cavalry, to Lt.-Ten. the Right Hon. Sir Fredk. Adam, K.C.B., Governor-in-Council of Fort St. George, on the Proceedings against Him on the Part of Lt.-Gen. the Hon. Sir Robt. Wilm. O'Callaghan, K.C.B., Commander-in-Chief of the Army of Fort St George, on Accusations of a Revolting Nature Offered against Him by Major John Watkins of the Fifth Regiment of Madras Light Cavalry: Whereof He Was Fully and Honourably Acquitted on Trial by Court-Martial ; with Correspondence Attached, Exhibiting the Charges Preferred by Lieut. Col. Smythe against Major Watkins, and Lieut.-Col. T.H.S. Conway, C.B., of the Eighth Regiment of Madras Light Cavalry, Adjutant-General of the Army of Fort St. George : And Urging Their Trial by General Court-Martial, 1834*, Hume Tracts, University College London Special Collections (<https://jstor.org/stable/60209517>)
- Spiers, Edward M. *The Army and Society 1815-1914*. London: Longman, 1980.
- Steppler, G. A. 'British Military Law, Discipline, and the Conduct of Regimental Courts Martial in the Later Eighteenth Century'. *English Historical Review* 102, no. 405 (1987): 859–86.
- Stocqueler, J. H. *The Hand-Book of British India: A Guide to The Stranger, the Traveller, the Resident, And All Who May Have Business with or Appertaining to India*. 3rd ed. London: Wm. H. Allen and Co, 1854.
- Stoler, Ann Laura. *Carnal Knowledge and Imperial Power: Race and the Intimate in Colonial Rule*. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press, 2002.
- Stoler, Ann Laura. 'Tense and Tender Ties: The Politics of Comparison in North American History and (Post) Colonial Studies'. *The Journal of American History* 88, no. 3 (2001): 829–65.
- Tadmor, Naomi. *Family and Friends in Eighteenth-Century England: Household, Kinship, and Patronage*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2001.
- 'The Indian Army'. *Blackwood's Edinburgh Magazine* 21, no. 125 (May 1827): 563–74.
- Travers, Robert. 'Indian Petitioning and Colonial State-Formation in Eighteenth-Century Bengal'. *Modern Asian Studies* 53, no. 1 (2019): 89–122.
- Upchurch, Charles. *Before Wilde: Sex between Men in Britain's Age of Reform*. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press, 2009.
- Villiers, Edward Hyde. *Report from the Select Committee on the Affairs of the East India Company*. Vol. 5. London: House of Commons, 1832.
- Walker, Claire. 'Whispering Fama: Talk and Reputation in Early Modern Society'. In *'Fama' and Her Sisters: Gossip and Rumour in Early Modern Europe*, edited by Heather Kerr and Claire Walker. Turnhout, Belgium: Brepols Publishers, 2015.
- Watkins, John. *To the Honorable the Chairman, Deputy Chairman and Court of Directors of the United East India Company: The Respectful Memorial of John Watkins, Late a Major in the 5th Regiment of Light Cavalry, Madras Establishment*. London: J. Darling, 1835.

- Welsch, Christina. *The Company's Sword: The East India Company and the Politics of Militarism, 1644–1858*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2022.
- White, William. *Mirzas Kaiwan Jah, or the Dethroned King of Oude, in Chains!!! Being a Letter to Lord Viscount Melbourne*. London: William Strange, 21, Paternoster Row, 1838.
- White, Adam. *Considerations on the State of British India*. London: J. M. Richardson, 1822.
- White, William. *A Letter Addressed to the Proprietors of India Stock, Demonstrating British Justice in India*. London: J. Miller, 1823.
- White, William. *Petition of Capt. William White to the Proprietors of East India Stock. Also, the Petition of Mayput Sing, Subedar, to the Marquis of Hastings, Praying against Injustice and Oppression*. London: J Miller, 1823.
- Wickremesekera, Channa. *'Best Black Troops in the World': British Perceptions and the Making of the Sepoy, 1746-1805*. New Delhi: Manohar, 2002.
- Yule, Henry, Sir. *Hobson-Jobson: A Glossary of Colloquial Anglo-Indian Words and Phrases, And Of Kindred Terms, Etymological, Historical, Geographical And Discursive*. New ed. edited by William Crooke, B.A. London: J. Murray, 1903.